

THE NATIONAL GAMES OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE ARE THE
EMBODIMENT OF VALUES

Iroda Oralbaeva

Yunus Xojabaev

Nukus branch of Uzbekistan State University
of Physical Education and Sports 2nd year students

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Abstract. In the article, the national games of the people in the years of independence, as well as a number of action games inherited from ancestors and sports-specific games, related to the national values, are considered as scientific heritages.

Keywords: Independence, play, student, people, national, value, heritage, social, physical.

НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ИГРЫ УЗБЕКСКОГО НАРОДА – ЭТО
ВОПЛОЩЕНИЕ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ

Аннотация. В статье в качестве научного наследия рассматриваются национальные игры народа в годы независимости, а также ряд игр-действий, унаследованных от предков, и спортивно-специфических игр, связанных с национальными ценностями.

Ключевые слова: Независимость, игра, студент, народ, национальная, ценность, наследие, социальное, физическое.

The National People's Games are one of the most popular public spiritual events of the people within the national cadres. "Navroz", Eid, weddings and various traditional ceremonies, Udums have not passed without wrestling, kopkari (goat), race and many other national games since ancient times. Such events are expressed in all types of folklore and epics. They are interestingly and comprehensively described in the works of the great scholars Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Alisher Nawai, Mirza Babur and later writers and poets.

In the recent past, and especially during the years of independence, by studying and reviving the national games of the people, they were purposefully used to educate the spiritual and physical maturity of schoolchildren. This year, the services of cultural and artistic figures, famous scientists M.Murodov, U.Koraboyev, T.S.Usmonkhoyayev, A.Q.Atoyev, J.Toshpolatov, R.Q.Qudratov, F.N.Nasriddinov, etc.

People's national games have several directions, and in their structure dances, lapars, sayings, askiyas and art of many genres are much more prominent. Also, among them, there are a

lot of action games and sports games inherited from ancestors. They can be divided into the following main groups:

1. Wrestlers (to Bukhara, Fergana, Khorezm, etc.).
2. Horse games (man-goat, race (yayov), girl chasing, overturning, horse riding, etc.).
3. Doorman (exercises on the gallows, jokes and sayings).
4. Lifting a stone.
5. Tug of war.
6. Wrist strength test.
7. Action games (ear stretching, donkey riding, shoulder wrestling, cockfighting, chilik, herd ball, etc.).

Almost all such games are widely used in public holidays, competitions and weddings. Their contents are known to the people.

They are also included in many educational and methodological manuals, monographs and popular scientific pamphlets.

Some educationally important action games are included in the "Physical Education" program of secondary schools, and they are becoming popular among young students. In addition, T.S. Usmonkhojaye, F. Khojaye and a number of other authors created collections such as "Action games" (1963-1981) and 1001 games (1991).

In the big weddings in Samarkand, Bukhara, Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, Jizzakh, Namangan, Syrdarya, Tashkent and other regions in the mountainous areas and newly developed areas, there will be wrestling, multi-goat, races and various action games. is used continuously. These games bring grace and blessings to weddings, and are receiving the applause of the audience, especially among the students, who are increasingly interested in national games and modern sports.

As mentioned at the beginning, great measures were taken to study and practice the national games of the people. On the initiative of U. Karaboyev, on April 25, 1991, the first National People's Games Republican competition was organized in Farish district (Jizzakh region). In this regard, the Republican State Sports Committee, Jizzakh regional administration, Jizzakh DPI team showed great activity and carried out material, financial and organizational activities. Such games were repeated in Forish every year in April and May. These games held in 1994-1996 were held under the name "People's National Games Republican Olympiad".

In May 1996. The 2nd Republican National Games Olympiad, dedicated to the 660th anniversary of the birth of Sahibqiron Amir Temur, was held with great success at the Kyzilqir

park near the center of Forish District, Yangikishloq. 11 teams took part in it to win 9 rounds and overall victory. The competition was watched by thousands of Jizzakh residents from other regions of the country, as well as guests from the USA, Norway, and Kazakhstan. First Deputy Chairman of the State Physical Education and Sports Committee of Uzbekistan Shavkat Tolaganov, Deputy Governor of Jizzakh Region Shirin Chilgashev, Governor of Forish District Bostankul Saidkulov congratulated the participants in the opening ceremony of the Olympics. Then the national anthem was played and the flag of the competition was raised. During the opening ceremony, the teams will pass the field one by one. The rounds of 1991 and 1994 took their place in the game program. Leading teams in the Republican Olympiad scored the following points before the final round: Jizzakh-157, Surkhandarya-103, Kashkadarya-87, Samarkand-80, Fergana-68 points. Apparently, the winning teams were known ahead of time.

The team of Forish, who defended the honor of Jizzakh, took the 9th place in the equestrian category of the regional championship. He won the Republican Olympiad without any difficulty. The Farishians were satisfied with the 5th place in the region in one stick match. At the Republican Olympiad, they defeated all their opponents by a large score. In the final match, they defeated the people of Samarkand by the biggest score (7:0).

Diplomas of the State Physical Education and Sports Committee of Uzbekistan and beautifully decorated gold, silver, and bronze medals were ceremoniously handed over to the teams that took 1-3 places during the competition. At the end of the Olympics, each member of the prize-winning teams was presented with valuable gifts from our committee. With the approval of the government of the republic and the proposal of sports organizations, it was agreed to hold the Olympiad of Alpomish games every two years.

In order to celebrate the 1000th anniversary of the creation of the "Alpomish" saga, the national games "The Motherland of Alpomish" and the "Alpomish Games Republican Festival" were held in Termiz. Games of 2000. It was established in the city of Fergana. The third festival was held in Gulistan in July 2002.

National People's Games Republican Competitions (1991-1996), and "Alpomish" Games Republican Festivals (1998) included wrestling, horse racing, kopkari (goat), "Storm", tug-of-war, wrist strength test, Mindy, Forty Stones (girl game) and other action games. Local amateur artists, well-known artists of the Republic, poets, cultural figures, writers from various fields took part in the opening and closing of the games and festivals, and it was held as a big celebration. These events were made into special videos and films by the TV and radio company and the creators of "Uzbektefilm". The festivals held in 1998 (Termiz) and 2000 (Fergana) were televised. The

video was recorded and replayed several times. Such nationwide national holidays and games became popular with the demonstration of how rich, meaningful and educationally high the essence of our national value is.

"Women's Year" (1999) based on the decree of the President of the Republic on the creation of the "Spirituality and Enlightenment" public center (1993) and the special decisions of the Republic's government in this area (1993-1995) in order to restore national values. Important events such as "Year of Healthy Generation" (2000), "Year of Mothers and Children", "Year of Valuing the Elderly" (2002) are being implemented.

It is known that the role of women in our social and cultural life is gaining incomparable importance. In order to remember the culture of the ancient ancestors, to cheer the spirit of the past nobles, in 1999 in Jizzakh, dedicated to the Women's Year, the "Tomaris Games Republican Festival" was organized. This event was also held in the spirit of high spirits and took on a festive tone. Women's teams from all regions of the republic gathered and held competitions in gymnastics, athletics, sports, swimming and other sports. Such a festival was organized again in 2001 in Shahrisabz (Kashkadarya region).

It should be noted that the National People's Games (Jizzakh, Termiz, 1992), the Republican Festivals "Alpomish Games" (1998, 2000, 2002), "Tomaris Games Republican Festivals" (1999, 2001, 2003) Republican scientific and practical conferences were also held. The contents of the national games of the people were explained in them. Also, a lot of lectures focused on the role of national games in the content of national values and their educational significance were collected. Their summaries were included in the scientific collections of the conference.

Despite this, the issue of teaching children to play kopkari-ulak, horse racing and other games is far behind. It would be appropriate if equestrian sports clubs were established among the village youth, and horse games were taught from a young age, and military-physical exercises on horseback were taught to young men of draft age. It should be recognized that the two-part film

"Alpomish" (directed by Usman Azimov) developed in 2000 fully expressed the content of national values. He described well the practical activities of "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" in wrestling, horse racing, and shooting. Young people should draw a good conclusion from this.

Instead of various jumps, runs and difficult gymnastic exercises, if girls are taught national movement games in classes, it can be one of the important activities in growing their physical maturity. Also, it is good to introduce the use of national movement games as part of favorite movement games and activities in families and kindergartens.

The conclusion is that people's national games serve as an important factor in human development and youth education. For this reason, it is necessary to deepen the socio-educational aspects of the national games to the students.

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